

MEDICAL SCIENCES

STRUCTURE AND DYNAMICS OF HUMAN RESOURCES AT THE UNIVERSITY MULTI-PROFILE HOSPITAL FOR ACTIVE TREATMENT “QUEEN YOANNA - ISUL” FOR THE PERIOD 2013-2022

Kirkov V.,

Chief Assistant in the Department of Social and preventive medicine and disaster medicine, Faculty of Public Health „Prof. Tzecomir Vodenitcharov, MD, DSc”, Medical University – Sofia

Markova K.,

Professors in the Department of Health Management and Health Economics, Faculty of Public Health „Prof. Tzecomir Vodenitcharov, MD, DSc”, Medical University – Sofia

Penev L.,

Doctoral candidate in the Department of Health Management and Health Economics, Faculty of Public Health „Prof. Tzecomir Vodenitcharov, MD, DSc”, Medical University – Sofia

Ivanova K.

Chief Assistant in the Department of Health technology assessment, Faculty of Public Health „Prof. Tzecomir Vodenitcharov, MD, DSc”, Medical University – Sofia

ABSTRACT

Human capital is a key factor for the efficiency and sustainable development of every healthcare institution. The structure and dynamics of hospital staff determine not only the quality of healthcare services, but also the ability of the institution to respond to systemic challenges and social needs. Special attention should be paid to imbalances between different categories of personnel, as well as to trends in turnover and shortage of specialists, which directly affect the organization of the treatment and diagnostic process. In this context, the present article analyzes the development of human resources in the period 2013-2022 at the University Hospital “Queen Yoanna – ISUL”.

Keywords: human resources, hospital, structure, dynamics.

Introduction

Human capital in healthcare facilities is a determining factor for the success of every hospital and plays a key role in fulfilling its primary functions. From providing quality clinical care to carrying out social and preventive tasks, hospitals are complex institutions that require well-organized and effectively functioning teams of medical and non-medical staff. In Bulgaria, where the healthcare system faces serious challenges such as shortages of healthcare professionals, uneven resource distribution, and limited financial means, the effective management of human resources is crucial for achieving high standards in medical practice [5; 19].

A specific feature of human capital in healthcare is its heterogeneous structure – the system employs not only doctors, nurses, midwives, rehabilitation specialists, and laboratory technicians, but also a wide range of other professionals such as chemists, physicists, biologists, psychologists, IT specialists, social workers, economists, lawyers, and others [4].

The main functions of the hospital – clinical care, prevention and health promotion, social services, staff training, and financial management – cannot be successfully fulfilled without proper organization, recruitment, and motivation of human resources. Qualified doctors, nurses, pharmacists, administrative and auxiliary staff, as well as effective communication between

them, ensure the quality of medical services and the ability to cope with daily challenges.

At the same time, hospitals carry out important social and educational functions, including training and development of future medical professionals and providing social support to patients. In these functions, human resources are not only the main driving force but also a key indicator of long-term success. When hospitals employ well-trained and motivated staff, they can guarantee better conditions for patients and offer a wider range of services, including disease prevention, support for chronically ill patients, and social integration of vulnerable and priority groups in society [8].

Despite these essential tasks, hospitals in Bulgaria face serious difficulties in human resource management. The migration of young doctors and nurses, exhausting shifts, low pay levels, and limited financial resources hinder the provision of the necessary quantity and quality of staff. This affects not only daily hospital operations, but also the ability to fulfill the economic and organizational functions of the institution – such as sustainable financial management and cost optimization [19; 7].

The aim of this article is to examine and analyze the structure and dynamics of human resources at the University hospital “Queen Yoanna – ISUL”, Sofia, in the period 2013-2022.

To achieve this aim, the following **tasks** were set and studied:

- ✓ To investigate and analyze the overall structure and dynamics of the hospital staff;
- ✓ To investigate and analyze the structure and dynamics of staff by categories: doctors, healthcare specialists, pharmacists, auxiliary staff, and hospital administration.

Materials and methods of the research:

The object of this research is the structure and dynamics of human resources at the University Hospital "Queen Yoanna – ISUL," Sofia, for the period 2013–2022, as well as the factors influencing them.

The study applied a wide range of sociological, statistical, and documentary methods.

Quantitative analyses were conducted using the statistical software package SPSS 17.0. For tabular and graphic processing and presentation, Microsoft Office products were used.

Results and discussion

The University Hospital "Queen Yoanna – ISUL" was established in the 1920s, when the idea matured for a hospital to serve insured workers. Since its establishment, the hospital has been a multiprofile institution of national importance. Its mission is to provide access to structures for diagnosis, treatment, and rehabilitation for all citizens, regardless of nationality, profession, or religion. The hospital ensures uninterrupted medical care 24 hours a day. The specialized and highly specialized medical activities of "Queen Yoanna – ISUL" and the experience of its highly qualified professionals have established it as a national center where complicated or difficult-to-diagnose cases are referred from Sofia and the country.

Healthcare system resources, transformed through management processes, determine outcomes. These resources are: material, human, financial, time, and information. Material and financial resources are necessary

conditions for the realization of human resource potential. Human resources ensure the provision and effective use of all other resources. The lack or insufficiency of one resource negatively affects the others and reduces the effectiveness of the healthcare system or organization [12].

The resource base (human, material, financial) of the University Hospital "Queen Yoanna – ISUL" allows for analysis, evaluation, and planning of capacity and development strategies. A more specific focus is the analysis of human resources, especially after the establishment of the emergency department with a diagnostic inpatient unit in 2010.

The resource provision (human, material and financial) of the University Hospital "Queen Yoanna - ISUL" provides an opportunity for analysis, assessment and planning of the capacity and strategies for development of the medical institution. The analysis of human resources is more specific, given the emergency department with a diagnostic inpatient unit established in 2010.

Human resource management is a key element in the administration of every healthcare facility, as it is the most important factor for success and forms part of the hospital's strategic management. Achievements in process optimization, financial responsibility, and meeting patient requirements depend directly on the qualification of employees and on the tools available in their daily work. Motivated staff, equipped with appropriate instruments and working in an environment that stimulates innovation, are the main prerequisite for optimizing processes and practices under conditions of limited financial resources, achieving success in patient care, and ultimately fulfilling the hospital's mission [19; 2].

For the period 2013 - 2022, the provision of human resources at the University Hospital "Queen Yoanna - ISUL" is as follows:

Figure 1. Total number of staff at the University Hospital "Queen Yoanna - ISUL" for the period 2013 - 2022
Source: Annual Financial Statement of University Hospital "Queen Yoanna - ISUL" EAD

From the presented graph it can be seen that during the ten-year period under review, the largest increase in the number of average staff occurred in 2016 compared to 2015 – by 60 people. In the period 2016-2018 the hospital had the highest number of personnel, after which it gradually began to decrease, and by 2022 the number was almost the same as at the beginning of the period – 957 people. The observed cycle of growth followed by a decrease in staff may be associated both with organizational changes and the hospital’s financial

capacity, as well as with demographic and labor market conditions in the healthcare sector. The high values in the period 2016–2018 were likely the result of active recruitment of new staff in response to increased demand for healthcare services. The subsequent decline and return to baseline levels in 2022 indicate difficulties in retaining staff and/or limited opportunities for increasing staffing levels. This is an indicator of instability in personnel policy and the need for a more sustainable human resource management strategy.

Figure 2. Number of doctors at the University Hospital "Queen Yoanna - ISUL" for the period 2013 – 2022
Source: Annual Financial Statement of University Hospital "Queen Yoanna - ISUL" EAD

Examining the structure of the staff, it is notable that in 2022 the number of doctors increased by 23.1% compared to 2013. Their highest number was recorded in 2018, after which it gradually began to decrease, but in 2022 there was an increase of 17 physicians compared to the previous year. The growth of more than 23% in the number of doctors over the ten-year period is a positive signal for the hospital, as it ensures better patient access to specialists. Nevertheless, the decrease

observed after 2018 may be considered an indicator of staff migration to the private sector or abroad, as well as a reflection of the general trend of shortage of medical specialists in the country. The increase in 2022 is likely the result of targeted policies to attract or retain doctors, but the question remains whether this is a sustainable trend. An analysis of the doctor–nurse ratio is necessary in order to assess the real effectiveness of the staffing structure.

Figure 3. Number of medical specialists in healthcare at the University Hospital "Queen Yoanna – ISUL" for the period 2013 – 2022
Source: Annual Financial Statement of University Hospital "Queen Yoanna - ISUL" EAD

With regard to the number of healthcare specialists, there was relative stability during the period 2013–2018. In 2019, however, their number decreased by 30 compared to the previous year, and by 2022 they were 22.8% fewer compared to the beginning of the period.

The significant reduction of nurses and midwives by almost one quarter compared to 2013 is an alarming indicator. This puts at risk the normal functioning of the treatment process, since these specialists are essential

for the daily care of patients. Such dynamics often lead to increased workload for the remaining nurses and to the risk of deteriorating quality of care. The trend corresponds to the national problem of shortage of nurses and emphasizes the need for urgent measures to improve working conditions and to encourage young professionals to choose and remain in the profession.

Figure 4.

Number of pharmacists at the University Hospital "Queen Yoanna – ISUL" for the period 2013 – 2022
Source: Annual Financial Statement of University Hospital "Queen Yoanna - ISUL" EAD

The number of pharmacists employed at UMHAT "Queen Yoanna – ISUL" during the studied period ranged between 3 and 5, remaining unchanged in the last three years. This stable, but small number of pharmacists indicates relative sustainability in this segment of the staff. Although their number is low, their role is significant, as they ensure efficiency in drug supply and

the provision of pharmaceutical support for the hospital's therapeutic activities. The lack of increase in recent years may be interpreted as a signal that the hospital relies on minimal capacity in this area, which potentially creates risks in cases of higher workload or staff absence.

Figure 5. Number of other staff at the University Hospital "Queen Yoanna – ISUL" for the period 2013 – 2022
Source: Annual Financial Statement of University Hospital "Queen Yoanna - ISUL" EAD

For the hospital's other staff, a gradual increase was observed during the period 2013-2017, followed by a slight decline. In 2020, their number reached its highest level, most likely due to the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic, which required sufficient medical personnel to treat the large number of patients. In 2022, the number of other staff at the hospital decreased by 36 people, or 10.9%, compared to 2013. The dynamics in the number of "other staff" demonstrate sensitivity to external factors, with the peak in 2020, related to the COVID-19 pandemic, standing out most clearly. This confirms the importance of this category of employees in maintaining the hospital's flexibility and adaptability in crisis situations. However, the decline in 2022 - by more than 10% compared to 2013 - may negatively affect the overall logistics and support provided to the medical staff. The reduction of this group signals that in future crises, the hospital may face limited capacity for rapid response.

Inferences and conclusions

The analysis of the structure and dynamics of human resources at the University Hospital "Queen Yoanna – ISUL" for the period 2013-2022 shows significant fluctuations in the size and composition of the staff. The total number of employees peaked in 2016-2018, but subsequently decreased and by 2022 returned almost to its initial levels. The increase in the number of doctors by more than 23% compared to 2013 is a positive signal for ensuring better access to medical services. At the same time, however, the significant decline in nurses - by nearly one quarter over the same period - represents a serious problem that may lead to difficulties in the organization and quality of the treatment process. This disproportion between the main staff categories clearly highlights a structural imbalance that requires targeted personnel policy. On the other hand, the number of pharmacists has remained stable, although at a low level, while the dynamics in "other staff" show sensitivity to external factors, with the COVID-19 crisis most clearly demonstrating the importance of this category of employees for maintaining the hospital's flexibility and adaptability. All these trends emphasize the need for long-term measures to retain staff, improve working conditions, and encourage young professionals as a key to the hospital's sustainable development.

The results of the analysis highlight the need for a targeted human resource policy to ensure sustainability and balance in the hospital's workforce. The increase in the number of doctors is a positive signal, but it is offset by the significant decline in nurses - a key problem that threatens the quality of healthcare services. The insufficient number and reduction of auxiliary staff also indicate vulnerable areas in the organizational structure. To guarantee effective and high-quality healthcare, it is necessary to introduce long-term measures for attracting and retaining personnel, improving working conditions, and adapting to the dynamic challenges of the healthcare system.

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